

CURRICULUM CONCEPT MODEL: HUMANISTIC CURRICULUM MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The Humanistic Curriculum provides solutions for educating students to find their own identity. With the Humanistic curriculum, students are taught to show their potential human nature as individuals that is not touched by other curricula. A person is judged by his character and actions. If the attitude and characteristics are good then it is said that someone has a good personality, and vice versa. However, a person's personality can change anytime and anywhere. Because personality is formed partly due to environmental factors. A person's personality can be seen and felt throughout their life. Therefore, the human personality is said to be a unity in the human soul and body. Learning does not have to be defined as subjects that must be covered, but something that is more meaningful for life, taught in ways that are demonstrative and relevant for students. The Humanistic Curriculum offers other options in relation to subject matter and personality formation.

Keywords: Model, Humanistic Curriculum, Learning System.

INTRODUCTION

Basically every human being has a humanist nature. Human nature is a trait that already exists in humans themselves but without realising it. Human nature is included in human character in shaping human identity itself. Humanist nature must be explored so that humanistic potential emerges in humans. Nowadays we often see human nature that does not reflect kindness and honesty as well as empathy for others, they tend to do everything without humanity in order to get everything they want.

People in developed countries have a commitment to self-actualisation. Parents repeatedly talk about the importance of self-understanding in helping children's emotional and mental development as well as in developing thinking skills. This is important in terms of freedom of expression. The Humanistic curriculum supports these people's ideals. It helps learners discover who they are, not just mould them into having intellectual abilities. The humanistic curriculum prioritises activity, exploration, puzzle-solving, play, and things that are important for innovation and self-discovery.

A person's personality does not just emerge to be good. One's personality must be moulded even from the womb. When a mother carries a child in her womb, she has already taught everything that is good. A mother already talks to her stomach as if she is talking to the child in front of her. Children who have a good

personality are not only formed from the upbringing of their parents but also their environment. In the play environment in this case in the neighbourhood of the house where he lives. Likewise in the school environment. A child is able to interact with his friends at school.

The main goal of educators is to help students to develop themselves, namely helping each student to know themselves as unique human beings, who have good personalities and help realise the potentials that exist within them.

The humanistic curriculum offers a very basic solution to the problem of irrelevant and incomprehensible learning. Learning should not be interpreted as subjects to be poured over, but something more meaningful than life, taught in ways that are demonstrative and relevant to them. The humanistic curriculum offers an alternative to the link between subject matter and personality formation.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is library research, what is meant by library research is research activities carried out by collecting data in the form of books, journals and previous research results related to the object of this research. The data collection method uses the help of the internet to trace various book references and previous research journals that are in accordance with the topic of research discussion.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Definition of Humanistic Curriculum

The curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding the objectives, content and learning materials as well as the methods used as guidelines for organising learning activities to achieve the objectives of certain educational activities. Linguistically, the word 'humanistic' comes from the word 'humanist' which means humanising or prioritising human values. While etymologically humanistic is a person who yearns for and strives for the realisation of a better living association. Humanism is also defined as an ideology that holds that humans are the most important subject. Then in relation to the curriculum, what is meant by a humanistic curriculum is a curriculum that is oriented towards the development of personality, attitudes, emotions / feelings of students (Sanjaya, 2008: 67).

Humanistic education is a model of education that is oriented and views humans as humans (humanisation), namely God's creatures with their nature. So humans as living beings, they must be able to continue, maintain, and develop their lives. So the position of education can build a humanisation process, which means respecting human rights, such as the right to apply and be treated fairly, the right to voice the truth, the right to love, and so on.

The humanistic curriculum was developed by humanistic education experts. This curriculum is based on the concept of personalised education, namely John Dewey (progressive education) and J.J. Rousseau (*romantic education*). This school gives the main place to students. They start from the assumption that the child or student is first and foremost in education. He or she is the subject at the centre of educational activities. They believe that students have the potential, ability and power to develop. Humanist educators also adhere to the concept of *Gestalt*, that the individual or child is a whole unit. Education is directed towards fostering a complete human being not only in terms of physical and intellectual aspects but also social and affective aspects (emotions, attitudes, feelings, values, etc.) (Fitri, 2013: 124).

As described above, that the humanistic curriculum originated from the flow of empiricist education then humanist education was born and the humanistic curriculum was born, so that the humanistic curriculum was developed by humanist education experts, which is based on the concept of personal education flow (Personalized Education), namely Jhon Dewey (Progressive Education) and J.J. Rousseau (Romantic Education). Where this flow gives more place to students, meaning that this flow assumes that humans are the first and foremost in education, humans are both subjects and objects in education and also humans have the potential, strength and ability in themselves not as said by nativists that humans are like empty glasses that must be filled by the teacher.

The humanists also consider that humans or individuals are a whole and comprehensive unit (*gestalt*), so that departing from this, education is directed at fostering a complete human being not only in physical and intellectual terms but also in social and affective terms. So that in humanistic education requires the establishment of a relaxed, permissive and familiar atmosphere. So that students can develop all the potential that exists in themselves.

According to humanists, the curriculum functions to provide valuable experiences (knowledge) to help facilitate the personal development of students. The purpose of education is a dynamic process of personal development and is directed towards the growth, integrity, and autonomy of the personality, a healthy attitude towards self, others and learning. Humanistic curriculum is believed to be a curriculum function that provides experiences to students to support intrinsically the achievement of personal development and independence. They view the purpose of education as a dynamic process of personal development directed towards growth, integration, personal autonomy, healthy attitudes towards self, others and learning.

The humanistic curriculum was developed by educationalists. humanistic. This school gives the main place to students. Teachers are expected to build good

emotional relationships with their students (Dr Rusman 2009:37).

Basic Concepts of Humanistic Curriculum

The concept of a humanistic approach to education emphasises positive development. It focuses on the potential of human beings to seek and discover their abilities and develop them. This includes social interpersonal skills and methods for self-development aimed at enriching the self, enjoying life and society. These positive self-development skills are particularly important in education because of their link to academic success.

Humanistic learning theory basically has the goal of learning to humanise people. Therefore, the learning process can be considered successful if the learner has understood their environment and themselves. This means that learners experience changes and are able to solve life problems and can adjust to their environment. In other words, the learner in the learning process must strive so that gradually he is able to achieve self-actualisation as well as possible.

The main goal of educators is to help students to develop themselves, namely helping each individual to know themselves as unique human beings and helping in realising the potentials that exist within them.

The application of humanistic theory in teacher learning directs students to think inductively, prioritises experience and requires active student involvement in the learning process. This can be applied through discussion activities, discussing material in groups so that students can express their respective opinions in front of the class. The teacher gives students the opportunity to ask questions if they do not understand the material taught. Learning based on humanistic theory which is the formation of personality, conscience, attitude change and analysis of social phenomena. The indicator of the success of this application is that students feel excited, take the initiative in learning and there is a pattern of change in mindset, behaviour and attitude of their own accord.

Positive abilities here are closely related to the development of positive emotions contained in effective dominants, such as the skills of building and maintaining warm relationships with others, how to teach trust, acceptance, awareness, understanding other people's feelings, interpersonal honesty, and other interpersonal knowledge. The point is to improve the quality of interpersonal skills in everyday life. Besides focusing on interpersonal relationships, humanist educators also try to create learning that helps students to improve their ability to create, imagine, experience, intuition, feel, and fantasise. Humanist educators try to look at the broader spectrum of human behaviour.

Looking at what humanist educators strive for, it appears that this approach emphasises the importance of emotions in education. So it can be said that emotions are a very strong characteristic of humanist educators. Since thinking and

feeling go hand in hand, to ignore emotional education is to ignore one of the greatest human potentials. We can learn to use our emotions and benefit from this humanist approach just as much as we would from a cognitively focused education (Herpratiwi, 2016:41).

There are several schools included in humanist education, namely confluent education, radical criticism, and modern mysticism.

First, Confluent Education. Confluent education was developed by confluent education experts who wanted to unite affective aspects (attitudes, feelings, values) with cognitive aspects and confluent education emphasises the wholeness of the person, the individual must respond as a whole, but confluent education less emphasis on knowledge containing affective aspects, according to them the curriculum does not prepare education about attitudes, According to them, the curriculum does not prepare education about attitudes, feelings, and values that students should have, the curriculum should prepare a variety of alternatives that students can choose from in the process of behaving and feeling and giving value judgements, namely by inviting students to express choices and be responsible for the attitudes, feelings and value judgements they have chosen. The aim is to help students develop emotional and spiritual intelligence in addition to intellectual intelligence (Brown, 1971).

Second, Radical Criticism Education. Radical criticism education stems from Rousseau's naturalism or romanticism. They see education as an effort to help children discover and develop their own potential. Education is to create a situation that allows children to develop optimally. In education there is no coercion, what exists is encouragement and stimulation to develop.

Third, Modern Mysticism Education. Modern mysticism education is a school that emphasises the training and development of emotional sensitivity, subtlety of character, through sensitivity training, yoga, meditation and so on. The aim is to help students discover their innermost potential and connect with the spiritual dimension (Miller, 2007).

Humanistic Curriculum Characteristics

According to humanists, the curriculum functions to provide valuable experiences (knowledge) to help facilitate students' personal development. For them the goal of education is a dynamic process of personal development directed at the growth, integrity and autonomy of the personality, a healthy attitude towards oneself, others and learning all of which are part of the ideal of the development of *a self-actualised person (self actualising person)* a person who has been able to self-actualise is a person who has achieved balance (harmony) the development of all aspects of his personality both cognitive, aesthetic, and moral aspects, a person can work well if he has a good character as well (Sukmadinata,

1997: 90).

The humanistic curriculum has several characteristics that cannot be separated from the characteristics of humanist education, including:

First, there is a harmonious relationship between teachers and students. To build a good learning atmosphere, the relationship between teachers and students must also be built as harmoniously as possible, so that the teacher does not seem scary, because psychological influences greatly affect students' absorption in learning, if you look at the phenomenon of learning in schools, there is the term killer teacher or killer lecturer, this is evidence that there are still in the learning process where teachers or lecturers are feared by students or students and have implications for student absorption.

Second, the existence of integrity, namely in the humanistic curriculum emphasises the unity of behaviour not only intellectual (cognitive) but also emotional and action, this is a commitment of humanist education which seeks to restore education to social reality.

Third, totality, meaning that the humanistic curriculum must be able to provide a comprehensive experience, not fragmented (Partial).

Fourth, the evaluation model. In evaluation, the humanistic curriculum is different from the usual. This model prioritises the process over the results. If the usual curriculum, especially academic subjects, has achievement criteria, then in the humanistic curriculum there are no criteria. Their goal is the development of the child to become an open, more independent human being. The activities they undertake should be beneficial to the students. Good learning activities are those that provide experiences that will help students expand their awareness of themselves and others and develop their potential. The assessment is subjective both from the teacher and the students (Nana, 2004: 91).

CONCLUSION

Humanistic curriculum is a model of education that is oriented and views humans as humans (humanisation), namely God's creatures with their nature. So humans as living beings, they must be able to continue, maintain and develop their lives. So departing from this, education is directed towards fostering a complete human being not only in physical and intellectual terms but also in social and affective terms. According to humanists, the curriculum serves to provide valuable experiences (knowledge) to help facilitate the personal development of students.

The concept of the humanistic approach to education emphasises positive development. The approach focuses on the potential of people to seek and discover their abilities and develop them. This includes social interpersonal skills and methods for self-development aimed at enriching the self, enjoying life and society.

These positive self-development skills are particularly important in education because of their link to academic success. There are several schools that fall under humanist education, namely Confluent Education, Radical Criticism and Modern Mysticism.

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